

Weft Insertion Warp Knit for Hybrid Composites

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ABSTRACT

A new textile preform for hybrid composites is introduced in this study. The tensile stress-strain behavior of a weft insertion warp knit (WIWK) hybrid preform was characterized over a wide range of glass/graphite and glass/Kevlar combinations. The WIWK preform fabrication process was found to be capable of handling high modulus materials with minimum damage to the fibers. The WIWK preform has excellent conformability while maintaining a high level of structural integrity. The equation of mixture was found to be applicable to the WIWK hybrid preform.

INTRODUCTION

Responding to the potential growth opportunities of composites in the aerospace, land and sea transportation and recreation, tremendous progress has been made in the past twenty years in the development of resin matrix and high performance fibers. Presently, the majority of the advanced composites are still limited to aerospace applications. The slow transformation of the predominantly aerospace composite market into a broad base civilian market can be attributed, partly, to the lack of recognition of the availability and the significance of the preform structures.

Currently, most of the advanced composites are still reinforced by biaxially woven fabrics. The conformability and the level of translation of material properties into the composite structure is limited by the crimp geometry of the biaxially woven fabrics and by the harshness of the weaving process. Recent progress in textile processing technology has made available several new reinforcement concepts. Examples of some candidate preform structures include the triaxial woven fabric, high modulus weft knit, warp knit, braids and nonwovens. In this study, the properties of a weft insertion warp knit (WIWK) hybrid preform is characterized. The design concept for the WIWK fabric has been detailed by Ko et al [1]. Coupled with fabric structural geometry, hybridization provides further flexibility in the tailoring of composites for a wide range of performance and cost constraints. The other advantages of hybridization have been reviewed by Chou et al [2]. In this study, we demonstrate the hybrid effect of the WIWK preform with a wide range of combinations of glass/graphite and glass/Kevlar.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Three widely used reinforcing materials were considered in this study. These yarns included: Type 30 (3600 denier) glass yarn; a 1450 denier Kevlar 49 yarn; and a Thornel 300 series 3600 denier graphite yarn. A summary of the tensile properties of the yarns is given in Table I. The stress-strain behavior of these yarns is also shown in Figure 1.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF YARN PROPERTIES

	Linear Density (tex)	Strength (gm/tex)	Elongation (%)	Modulus (g/tex)	Toughness (g/tex)
Glass	409	59.8	2.94	2328	0.896
Kevlar	158	164.0	2.13	7547	1.700
Graphite	402	29.7	0.46	10552	0.078

$$\text{GPa} = .01 \times \text{specific gravity} \times \text{gm/tex}$$

The experimental fabrics were prepared on a laboratory Raschel warp knitting machine. This fabrication system is known for its high productivity (over 10X the productivity of weaving) and its design flexibility. Figure 2 illustrates the wide range of geometric arrangement of the reinforcing yarns (heavy lines). Figure 2A shows a simple weft laid-in structure with tricot stitch yarns (fine diagonal lines) which provide structural integrity to the fabric. Figures 2B and 2C show the three-bar WIWK structures with laid-in yarns in both machine (warp) and cross-machine (weft) directions in straight and nonlinear configuration. Note that the programmable nonlinear warp yarn geometry is achieved in plane rather than by interlacing. This feature provides a means for tailoring elongation and toughness without severe reduction in material properties as in the case of woven fabrics. Figure 2D shows another geometric arrangement of WIWK wherein the warp laid-in yarns deflect in the opposite direction to form a balanced structure.

In this study, the geometry shown in Figure 2A was used with five levels of fractional combinations of glass/graphite and glass/Kevlar ranging from 100/0, 75/25, 50/50, 25/75 and 0/100. To produce a 75/25 combination, a series of three yarns of the first material were laid-in and then one of the other material arranged in a repeating 3/1 pattern. In the case of a 50/50 combination, two arrangements - 2/2 and 1/1 - were used to examine the effect of material distribution.

The preform test samples were prepared by cutting a one-inch stripe along the weft direction. Care was taken to insure the same number of yarns were included in each specimen. Reinforced epoxy resin end-tapes were placed 130mm apart on the specimen to minimize jaw effect during testing and to outline the gage length. The samples were tested in the weft direction on an Instron tensile tester using serrated grips at a strain rate of .017 per second. All the tests were carried out at standard textile testing lab conditions (65% RH, 70°F). Ten replications were made for each material combination.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Tensile Stress-Strain Behavior

The physical and mechanical properties of the hybrid fabrics are summarized in Tables II and III. The areal density of the fabrics were maintained fairly constant, on the order of 400 g/m², in the various material combinations. The thickness of the fabrics reflects the bulkiness of the structure which is related to the specific gravity of the material. At approximately the same weight

Figure 1. Stress-strain relationships of high modulus yarns

Figure 2. Various structural geometry of WIWK

per unit area, the glass fabric was, as expected, the least bulky while the Kevlar fabric was the bulkiest.

Table II. SUMMARY OF HYBRID FABRIC PROPERTIES
(Glass/Graphite)

Combination (%)	Weight (g/sq.m)	Thickness (mm)	Strength (g/tex)	Elongation (%)	Modulus (g/tex)	Toughness (g/tex)
100.0	413	0.71	58	2.88	2369	0.90
75.1	395	0.88	40	2.69	3223	0.64
50.6	396	0.89	29	2.73	4170	0.53
25.2	395	0.94	25	0.77	5346	0.11
0.0	396	0.88	29	0.77	7543	0.15

$$\text{GPa} = .01 \times \text{specific gravity} \times \text{gm/tex}$$

Table III. SUMMARY OF HYBRID FABRIC PROPERTIES
(Glass/Kevlar)

Combination (%)	Weight (g/sq.m)	Thickness (mm)	Strength (g/tex)	Elongation (%)	Modulus (g/tex)	Toughness (g/tex)
100.0	413	0.71	58	2.88	2369	0.90
79.4	383	0.97	65	2.69	2902	0.97
56.3	378	0.95	99	3.67	3544	1.86
30.0	362	0.90	130	4.23	4264	3.12
0.0	343	0.90	152	4.42	4627	3.84

$$\text{GPa} = .01 \times \text{specific gravity} \times \text{gm/tex}$$

The strength, rupture elongation and toughness of the glass/graphite fabrics decreased as the proportion of fiberglass decreased. The opposite trend was observed for the glass/Kevlar fabrics. The modulus of the fabrics increased as the proportion of the higher modulus material increased. The increase was more drastic with the glass/graphite fabrics.

The hybrid effect is more dramatically illustrated in Figures 3A and 3B. In Figure 3A, it can be seen that the fabrics are gradually stiffen as the proportion of graphite increases. The hybrid effect, which is the combination of the high modulus characteristics of graphite and the toughness and strength of glass, was the most effective between 50/50 to 80/20 glass/graphite combinations. This effect seems to agree with the mechanism proposed by Chou and Kelly [2].

As shown in the stress-strain curves for the 1/1 and 2/2 arrangement, material distribution did not seem to have as great an effect on the glass/graphite fabric as in the glass/Kevlar fabrics. A 2/2 glass/Kevlar arrangement tended to produce a stiffer and stronger fabric.

As shown in Figure 3B, the hybrid effect did not seem to occur in the glass/Kevlar fabrics from the tensile stress-strain behavior point of view. However, the advantage of combining glass and Kevlar may be derived in the reduction of cost of material. Assuming the cost of E-glass, Kevlar and graphite to be \$1/lb., \$10/lb. and \$25/lb., respectively, the strength per cost for the various combinations of glass/graphite and glass/Kevlar is shown in Figure 4. It is interesting to note that while the glass/Kevlar hybrid preforms consistently give higher strength per cost than the glass/graphite fabrics, the critical performance/cost for both glass/graphite and glass/Kevlar preforms was at the 75% glass content. This suggests that a significant performance per cost level can be realized when over 75% by weight of glass is used in Kevlar or graphite hybrids.

Figure 3. Stress-Strain Relationship of Hybrid Fabrics

The Equation of Mixture

The ultimate tensile strength of the hybrid fabrics can be estimated by the conditional equation or the equation of mixture shown in Figure 5. Good agreement between predicted and experimental strength results is shown in Figure 6. From the strength point of view, it can be seen that the critical weight fraction for glass/graphite hybrid is 50/50 and approximately 80/20 for glass/Kevlar.

CONCLUSIONS

New developments in fabric structures have provided additional design concepts for composites. The properties of composites can be engineered by proper selection of material, fabric geometry and fabric finishing technique. Hybridization provides additional flexibility in tailoring composites for specific applications under performance/cost constraints.

From the performance/availability/cost point of view, weft insertion warp knit (WIWK) fabric is a practical candidate fabric for flexible and rigid composites. The WIWK system provides a high level of strength translation efficiency, design flexibility and high productivity (speed x width).

In order to maximize the cost effectiveness of composites, hybrids of Kevlar or graphite with glass content of over 75% by weight should be considered.

The equation of mixture is applicable for the prediction of the strength of WIWK hybrid preforms.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to thank Owens-Corning Fiberglass Co., DuPont and Union Carbide for supplying the material for this study.

FIGURE 5

THEORETICAL STRENGTH

$$S_C = \text{MAX} \left[(T_A S_A + T_B S_{B1}), T_B S_{B2} \right]$$

T_A = Fractional Linear
Density of A

T_B = Fractional Linear
Density of B

Where A has lower breaking
elongation than B

REFERENCES

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Figure 6. Theoretical and experimental ultimate strength of glass/graphite and glass/Kevlar hybrid fabrics